

NOTES

Complexes of Dioxouranium(VI) with *p*-Methylbenzohydroxamic Acid

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Manuscript received 11 September 1989,
revised 21 November 1990, accepted 6 December 1990

THE present paper describes the isolation and characterisation of a series of dioxouranium(VI) complexes with *p*-methylbenzohydroxamic acid (LH) of the general formula $M[UO_2(L)_3] \cdot nH_2O$, where M=monovalent cations, viz. Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Rb^+ , Ag , Tl , Cs^+ , NH_4^+ , $C_6H_5N^+$ (anilinium) and $C_5H_5N^+$ (pyridinium).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The ligand *p*-methylbenzohydroxamic acid was prepared by the reported method¹ and its purity was checked, m.p. 138–39° (Found: C, 63.50; H, 5.92; N, 9.32; O, 21.26. Calcd.: C, 63.57; H, 5.96; N, 9.27; O, 21.2%).

Preparation of complexes:

To a suspension of *p*-methylbenzohydroxamic acid (2 g) on water (25 ml), dilute NaOH or KOH was added dropwise with constant stirring on a boiling water-bath until the acid went into solution (pH~9.0). To it 5% aqueous uranyl nitrate (10 ml) was added slowly with constant stirring. The resulting solution on stirring and evaporating gave deep red crystals of sodium or potassium tris(*p*-methylbenzohydroxamato)dioxouranium(VI). The crystals were filtered, washed with water and absolute alcohol and dried over concentrated H_2SO_4 . In case of the ammonium compound a solution of the ligand (2 g) in boiling water and ammonia solution (50 ml) was used. The Li, Rb, Cs and Tl complexes were made by adding 5% aqueous solutions (10 ml) of the salts of the respective metals to a deep red ammonium tris(*p*-methylbenzohydroxamato)dioxouranium(VI) solution (50 ml; pH~8.5) in the hot condition. In case of the Ag complex, 5% ammonical $AgNO_3$ solution (10 ml) was used. For pyridinium and anilinium complexes aqueous solution of the respective hydrochloride was used.

Uranium was estimated gravimetrically² and other metals were determined by AAS method using a Varian 1475 instrument. Nitrogen was estimated by Dumas' micromethod. Water of crystallisations were evaluated from TGA data.

Molar conductance (DMF) was measured with a Systronic 304 conductivity meter (accuracy $\pm 1\%$).

The results are presented in Table 1. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Beckmann IR 20 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (DMF) on a Hilger UVISPEK spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The stoichiometry ($M[UO_2(L)_3] \cdot nH_2O$) of the complexes (Table 1) was established on the basis of elemental analyses. The complexes are coloured, well-defined crystalline solids having ample solubility in DMF and DMSO. All the complexes are found to be insoluble in water and other common solvents like ethanol, methanol, acetone and benzene.

All the complexes except those with rubidium caesium and thallium took up water of crystallisation. The hydrated complexes started losing weight at around 60–70°, the water of crystallisation was completely driven out at about 110°. The ammonium salt decomposed at 70° but all other compounds decomposed at 110–190° with a sharp and substantial loss in weight at the decomposition temperature due to the loss of all the three molecules of the ligand at a time. This indicated the equivalence in the attachment of three *p*-methylbenzohydroxamato units to the uranyl moiety. The residues attained constant weight at about 525° and had the composition of the corresponding metallic diuranates for the metallic salts and U_3O_8 for the salts with ammonium and organic cations.

Molar conductance values of the complexes (Table 1) were found to be lower than those expected³ for 1:1 electrolytes possibly due to lower mobility of the bulky anionic part⁴.

The IR spectra of the complexes containing water of crystallisation showed bands at 3400–3610 cm^{-1} due to ν_{OH} . The ν_{N-H} ligand band at 3280 cm^{-1} was lowered to 3220–3250 cm^{-1} in the complexes. A strong band due to $\nu_{C=O}$ of the ligand at 1640 cm^{-1} was shifted to 1590–1595 cm^{-1} in the complexes, indicating the keto group of the ligand as the site of coordination to UO_2^{2+} entity⁵. The bands at 1475–1560 cm^{-1} are assigned to δ_{N-H} for the amide-II modes. A band of medium intensity at 1370 cm^{-1} in the free ligand due to ν_{C-N} or amide-III increased to 1380–1395 cm^{-1} on complex formation as expected⁵. A band at 1165 cm^{-1} in the ligand attributed to the hydroxamic group (δ_{NOH}) was also shifted in the complexes to a lower value 1150 cm^{-1} indicating deprotonation of the N–O–H group. The strong bands at 895–935 cm^{-1} in all the complexes were attributed to the non-degenerate asymmetric stretching mode ($\bar{\nu}_3$) of the UO_2^{2+} ion. The strong band at 905 cm^{-1} due to ν_{N-O} of the free

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, AND CONDUCTANCE DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd *	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Mol. cond. $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
		M	U	N	H ₂ O	
Li[$\text{UO}_2(\text{L})_3$] 2H ₂ O	Orange yellow	0.91 (0.92)	30.95 (31.20)	5.46 (5.51)	4.69 (4.72)	56.64
Na[$\text{UO}_2(\text{L})_3$].H ₂ O	Red-brown	2.99 (3.02)	31.24 (31.27)	5.48 (5.51)	2.35 (2.37)	50.39
K[$\text{UO}_2(\text{L})_3$].H ₂ O	Brownish red	5.05 (5.02)	30.51 (30.63)	5.36 (5.41)	2.30 (2.32)	52.05
Rb[$\text{UO}_2(\text{L})_3$]	Orange yellow	10.56 (10.61)	29.46 (29.55)	5.24 (5.21)	—	30.56
Cs[$\text{UO}_2(\text{L})_3$]	Orange	15.49 (15.58)	27.83 (27.90)	4.87 (4.92)	—	29.72
Ag[$\text{UO}_2(\text{L})_3$] 3H ₂ O	Deep brown	12.15 (12.23)	26.88 (26.99)	4.72 (4.76)	6.09 (6.12)	49.59
Tl[$\text{UO}_2(\text{L})_3$]	Orange	21.97 (22.12)	25.67 (25.75)	4.49 (4.54)	—	18.45
NH ₄ [$\text{UO}_2(\text{L})_3$].H ₂ O	Deep red	—	31.39 (31.48)	7.34 (7.41)	2.36 (2.38)	70.25
AnH[$\text{UO}_2(\text{L})_3$].H ₂ O	Brown	—	28.52 (28.61)	6.68 (6.73)	2.14 (2.16)	20.18
PyH[$\text{UO}_2(\text{L})_3$] H ₂ O	Deep red	—	29.02 (29.10)	6.79 (6.85)	2.18 (2.20)	22.55

* L = C₆H₅O₂N (*p*-methyl benzohydroxamate) ; Py = pyridine ; An = aniline.

ligand⁶ was masked or coupled with the $\bar{\nu}_3$ mode (895–935 cm⁻¹) of dioxouranium(VI) ion. The absence of non-degenerate symmetric stretching band ($\bar{\nu}_1$) in all the complexes indicated linearity of the UO_2^{2+} moiety⁷. Force constant and the length of U–O bond calculated⁸ by using the ν_3 values were found to be in the range 6.5–7.3 m dynes/Å and 1.73 ± 0.02 Å respectively. The values are in well accord with those obtained from the crystallographic measurements on various uranyl complexes⁹.

The electronic spectra of all the complexes exhibited one strong band at 24 480–26 570 cm⁻¹ which could be attributed to charge transfer transition from the ligand to uranium¹⁰.

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to K. Moitra, Principal, Chakdaha College, Nadia, West Bengal, for facilities, to Miss A. Gupta of the Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Calcutta-700 032, to Dr. B. Chakraborty and Dr. A. Guha of the Department of Chemistry, Kalyani University, for physicochemical measurements.

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